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Abstract:

In the framework of the Task 6.4 (WP6) of AIDAInnova, four sensor productions with high timing and tracking resolutions are planned by two vendors, CNM and FBK. This document reports on the readiness of the technological choices and wafer layouts and the completion of MS22 in Month 18.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2023

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Delivery Slip

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	4
1. LAYOUT OF 3D-TRENCH DETECTOR PRODUCTION AT FBK	4
2. LAYOUT OF LGAD DETECTOR PRODUCTION AT FBK	8
3. LAYOUT OF LGAD DETECTOR PRODUCTION AT CNM	10
2. REFERENCES	12
ANNEX: GLOSSARY	13

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main deliverable of the WP is the production and qualification of Hybrid Pixel sensors for excellent tracking and timing performance in future HEP experiments. For the sensors, four productions are planned by two vendors, CNM and FBK. To finalize the technological choices, validation of prototypes has been carried out, including detailed tests in the laboratories and with tests on beams, and also simulation studies that can be improved once compared to experimental data.

The technological choices for the LGAD and 3D production are now finalized. In FBK, the goal is to fabricate a batch of 3D sensors with trenched electrodes allowing to reach outstanding performance of time resolution < 20 ps on test structures. For the LGAD FBK production, the goal is to fabricate a batch of Trench-Isolated LGADs, while CNM will produce Inverted LGAD sensors. The wafer layout is complete in three out of four cases. The layout of the 3D production at CNM will be ready in the first half of 2023.

Unfortunately, the current unavailability of readout electronics able to exploit the excellent time performance of pixelated sensors forces the layout to accommodate either small matrixes of 32 or 64 pixels or large structures compatible with existing chips with worse timing performance. The baseline pixel size is $55 \mu\text{m} \times 55 \mu\text{m}$. Several test structures will allow to further study the sensor performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

WP6 has as main deliverables the production and qualification of Hybrid Pixel sensors for excellent tracking and timing performance in future HEP experiments. One of the main goals is the production of four runs of LGAD and 3D sensors at FBK and CNM. The design and technological choices are based on simulations, the process of test wafers and the characterization of prototype devices with different technologies. Three of the four layouts have been completed and presented in this report, the design of the 3D sensor production at CNM is expected to be completed in the first semester of 2023.

1.1 LAYOUT OF 3D-TRENCH DETECTOR PRODUCTION AT FBK

3D pixels with trenched electrodes will be the object of the FBK batch, featuring two different options for the ohmic trenches, either continuous (STD) or dashed (DSH). The two concepts are sketched in Figure 1. The baseline pixel size is $55 \mu\text{m} \times 55 \mu\text{m}$.

As compared to previous productions [3D1, 3D2] of the TIMESPOT project, the batch will be implemented with an improved process and pixel layout.

Fig. 1. Sketch of different 3D-trench pixels: a) continuous ohmic trench, b) dashed ohmic trench ($g_1=15 \mu\text{m}$, $g_2=10 \mu\text{m}$).

The layout has been designed for stepper lithography, with a reticle area of $\sim 4 \text{ cm}^2$.

The plan is to have 18 reticle shots per wafer, and to process 12 wafers.

Figure 2 shows the full set of devices included in the reticle: ~70% of the area is dedicated to pixel sensors, whereas the remaining ~30% to test structures (TS). Pixel sensors come with two different array sizes (64x64 and 32x32). The former one is intended to be compatible with future ROCs of the IGNITE and Picopix types, and have a multiplicity of 6 per type. The latter one is compatible with existing ROCs of the TIMESPOT1 type [TIMESPOT1], and have a multiplicity of 12 per type. The arrangement is as regular as possible to ease the dicing.

Fig. 2. Layout of the full set of devices

As an example, Figures 3 and 4 show the layouts of 64x64 pixel arrays of STD layout and DSH layout, with details of a corner. In the STD detectors, the active area is terminated by a continuous ohmic trench frame, whereas in the DSH detector by a double row of staggered dashed ohmic trenches.

Fig. 3. Layout of a 64x64 STD pixel array, with detail of a corner.

Fig. 4. Layout of a 64x64 DSH pixel array, with detail of a corner.

The same solutions are adopted for the 32x32 pixel arrays. However, in order to make the die size larger for handling purpose, the true number of pixels is 37x32, and the dead area at the top of the sensor is made larger.

Fig. 5. Layout of single pixel test structures of STD type.

Test structures include single pixels, strips, and diodes, as well as technological test structures. An example of STD pixels is shown in Figure 5: there are groups of 7 pixels, with the outermost ones readout in pairs, and the three central ones readout individually. One version (right) has small metal pads placed directly on top of the pixels, the other one larger pads routed out at the periphery (left).

Fig. 6. Layout of strip test structure of STD type.

An example of strips of the STD type is shown in Figure 6: there are 7 strips each made of 10 shorted pixels. The two outermost strips are readout in pairs, while the three central strips are readout individually. The same pixel configuration (7 x 10) is used for diodes, where all pixels are shorted to a large metal pad.

Besides the baseline pixel geometry of $55\ \mu\text{m} \times 55\ \mu\text{m}$, test structures also include smaller pixels of $42\ \mu\text{m} \times 42\ \mu\text{m}$. As an example, Figure 7 shows the layout of a diode of STD type, made of an array of 7×12 pixels shorted together.

Fig. 7. Layout of diode test structure of STD type with 42 pixels of $42\ \mu\text{m} \times 42\ \mu\text{m}$.

1.2 LAYOUT OF LGAD DETECTOR PRODUCTION AT FBK

For the LGAD FBK production, the goal is to fabricate a batch of Trench-Isolated LGADs, that have been first introduced in [TI-LGAD1], sketched in Figure 8. Within an RD50 project, a batch of devices has been fabricated aiming at small pixels ($\leq 100\ \mu\text{m}$) and high Fill Factor ($> 80\%$). The tests carried out at INFN Torino [TI-LGAD2] and the University of Zurich [TI-LGAD3] have shown excellent pixel isolation pre- and post-irradiation (neutrons and X-rays), and very small no-gain inter-pixel distance from $10\ \mu\text{m}$ to $2\ \mu\text{m}$ for different designs (i.e., from 5 to 20 times lower than in standard LGADs), while confirming a very good timing resolution.

Fig. 8. Sketch of Trench-Isolated LGAD pixels.

Based on the output of these tests, the technological solutions that work best have been identified and the guidelines for the design of the AIDAinnova batch have been drawn. The AIDAinnova TI-LGAD layout has been finalized and it includes pixel matrices compatible with different timing chips. The

photolithography employs a reticule of $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ dimensions that is repeated regularly on the wafer surface. The mask includes a sensor with $55 \mu\text{m} \times 55 \mu\text{m}$ pixel size and $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ area to be interconnected to the Timepix4 chip. Smaller 32×32 or 64×64 matrices, still with $55 \mu\text{m} \times 55 \mu\text{m}$ pixel size, have the footprint of the Ignite, the successor of TIMESPOT1, and Picopix ASICs. Simpler pad devices have also been implemented, to be connected by wire bonding to read-out systems. A 5×5 matrix of $1.3 \times 1.3 \text{ mm}^2$ pads is compatible with the presently available versions of the ALTIROC chip of the ATLAS HGTD Collaboration and the ETROC chip of the CMS MTD project.

The design of the reticule is shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Layout of the $\sim 2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ reticule in the FBK TI-LGAD production

Different technological splits will be applied, with variations on the trench depth and process, and the addition of carbon doping in the area of the gain layer. Carbon doping has been demonstrated to retard the Boron deactivation caused by radiation that induces the loss of the gain capabilities of the sensors beyond a fluence of $1.0\text{-}1.5 \times 10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

The technological splits to be implemented in the TI-LGAD production are reported in Table 1.

Wafer	Thickness	Carbon	Trench depth	Trench process
1	45	Y	D2	P2
2	45	Y	D2	P2
3	45	Y	D1	P2
4	45	Y	D1	P1
5	45	Y	D2	P1
6	45		D2	P2
7	45		D2	P2
8	45		D1	P1
9	55	Y	D3	P2
10	55	Y	D2	P2
11	55	Y	D2	P2
12	55		D2	P2

Table 1: Technological splits of the TI-LGAD AIDAInnova production at FBK. The column “Thickness” refers to the thickness of the active part of the silicon bulk, “Carbon” to implementation of the carbon co-implantation in the gain-layer area, the “trench depths” vary from the shallower option D1 to the deeper one, D3, the “trench process” refers to the trenches isolation settings.

1.3 LAYOUT OF LGAD DETECTOR PRODUCTION AT CNM

IMB-CNM has designed and fabricated a new mask-set for inverted LGAD (iLGAD) sensors. This technology has been optimized with Sentaurus TCAD simulation toolkit. The iLGAD structure is based on the conventional LGAD process technology but with the difference that the segmentation is now located at the p+ side. Therefore, the multiplication is no longer coupled to the segmented electrodes and the gain is the same over the full area, providing a position-sensitive detector with uniform amplification wherever a particle hits the detector. The sensor has a 100% fill factor and the active area can be maximized thanks to the trenches placed at the edges of the pixel matrix. The technology and the mask-set are shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Technological sketch and Layout of the wafer

The mask set includes detectors with the following geometries:

- **TimePix3.** 55x55 μm pitch, 256x256 pixels: total **12**.
- **TDCPix.** 300x300 μm pitch, 40x45 pixels: total **8**.
- **UZH-PSI.** 100x100 μm pitch, 30x30 pixels: total **36**.
- **iStrip.** 80 μm pitch, 20 strips: total **40**.

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
HEP	High Energy Physics
IMB-CNM	Institute of Microelectronics of Barcelona (Centro Nacional de Microelectronica)
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler